

Humanistic Green Open Space as Healing Environment for its Urban Community

Case: Situ Gintung South Tangerang City

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Abstract:- The rapid growth in urban development, tends to decrease Green Open Spaces in South Tangerang City region. Continuous development, has caused decline in the ecosystem, poor air quality, traffic congestion, and various other factors that can cause physical and mental health problems for urban people such as depression, obesity, diabetes, hypertension. Various studies have shown that being outdoor can reduce stress levels (Wells et al, 2003) as well as levels of depression and anxiety (Park et al, 2010). The decrease of green spaces, due to development in the city of South Tangerang, and the lack of maintenance of the surrounding green open spaces and environmental parks in the area, led to the emergence of the idea of conducting research on the Situ Gintung area as one of the few green open spaces or parks in this city. This research was carried out using a descriptive qualitative method, by making observations and surveys around the research location, collecting on location data, and finding supporting literatures necessary in order to obtain information that could help achieve the right solution to overcome existing problems, in hope that it can be a recommendation and reference for the development of this area in the future. Improving the existing green open spaces into a humanistic and sustainable green open spaces that can be enjoyed by all groups of people, will benefit the physical, mental health and well-being of the community.

Keywords:- South Tangerang City, Situ Gintung, Humanistic Green Open Spaces.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

Situ Gintung a lake built in 1932 - 1933 by the Dutch East Indies in East Ciputat District, Pisangan Village, South Tangerang City, Banten Province, initially serve as rainwater absorption, flood prevention for Batavia or Jakarta and irrigation for the surrounding rice fields. In 2009, due

to its age, extreme rainfall, and lack of maintenance, the retaining wall of Situ Gintung in the downstream area / Jalan Gunung Raya, partially collapsed and flooded kampung Poncol area, damaging several buildings of Muhammadiyah University and housing in the surrounding vicinity, leaving around 100 casualties. In December 2009, The Government through Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing (PUPR), repaired the damages caused by the disaster and the repairment process was finished in 2011. Over the years, there have been changes in land use in Situ Gintung. gradually, the existing green spaces have been turned to residential area, tourist and sport attraction, many of the outdoor space elements are non-existent or damaged. South Tangerang City is one of the cities in Banten sub-district that is growing rapidly. With the increasing density of this city, more and more Humanistic Green Open Spaces are needed to support the physical and mental health of the community.

In general, the Situ Gintung area is one of the few green open spaces in this city, research on this area is carried out to further improve its condition so that it becomes more beneficial for the mental and physical health of the community, because a humanistic green area that is well organized will also improve the quality of the urban environment, thus increasing the comfort, beauty and freshness for its users, as well as harmony with nature. so that it can be further be improved into a humanistic and sustainable open space to support the physical, mental health and well-being of the community. Nowadays changes in modern human life style is filled with distractions and demands.

More and more people are spending their time indoors surrounded by artificial lights, electronic gadgets and technology. However, research shows that lack of exposure to nature can interfere with people's mental health and well-being. Green Open Spaces have several important benefits for human health, as these spaces provide opportunities for physical activity needed to maintain one's health and well-

being. Gardening, for example, can be beneficial for people with reduced mobility because it can teach them how to use or strengthen their muscles. Gardening can also provide calming and focus benefits for healthy individuals. In addition, connection to nature and being in green open spaces is known to improve mental health by providing a sense of relaxation, calmness and reducing stress levels. Places like these can also serve as social places that helps to overcome loneliness and isolation. The open space of the city should also be designed for human involvement. Overall, Green open spaces can contribute to the holistic health and sustainability of the urban community.

B. Problem Formulation

Considering that Green Open Spaces such as City Parks and environmental parks can provide various benefits for the physical and mental health of the surrounding community, it is necessary to examine the ease of accessibility of all levels of society to the Situ Gintung Area as well as the availability of signages, guide paths and socialization spaces that are adequate, safe, comfortable, where all levels of society can enjoy their time in nature to improve their physical and mental health. Therefore the Problem formulation will be as follows:

- Can changes in land function affect comfort and the availability of adequate green open space.?
- Can lack of outdoor space elements make an open space less humanistic and sustainable. ?

C. Research Objectives and Benefits.

The research on the Situ Gintung area is intended to improve and increase the quality of the area after repairs were carried out due to the collapse of part of the dam in 2009. It is hoped that the research carried out can be beneficial for the continuation of the maintenance of the area, because activities in the outdoors can increase the sense of comfort and improve cognitive function and human memory. (Berman et al,2)

D. Scope of Discussion

The scope of discussion in this research is limited to.:

- The study of local government policies, rules and regulation, to support the rearrangement of situ Gintung.
- Identifying the need of the community in Situ Gintung to make the green open space more humanistic and sustainable.
- Improving access and outdoor elements to accommodate public use and enhance visitor comfort.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Green Open Space

Green Open Space in Urban Area is part of a green open space of an area or urban area where various plants that are useful as support for the ecological, social, cultural, economic and aesthetic functions of an Urban Green Open Space grow.

Based on the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 1 of 2007, regarding the Arrangement of Green Open Space in Urban Areas (RTHKP), open space, is spaces, area or areas which its use not intensively developed for residential areas, commercial, industrial or institutional areas or in other words areas without buildings.

The arrangement of Green Open Space is regulated by Law No. 26 of 2007. Spatial planning provides a rule that 30% of the City Area must consist of 20% Public Open Space and 10% Private Open Space. Green open space or Public RTH is an RTH that is managed by the local government, city or district, used and utilized for the benefit of the wider community. Examples of Green Open Space or Public RTH are: city parks, urban forests, green belts, RTH around rivers, cemetery areas and railways.

Private Green Open Space or Private RTH is a Green Open Space managed by Institutions or individuals, and is used only by certain groups such as gardens or yards, office yards, or buildings both owned by the community and private milk planted with plants.

Public and Private Green Open Spaces have several important functions for the sustainability of a city such as:

➤ Ecological Function.

As the lungs of the city, the existence of RTH can help in producing oxygen, absorbing rainwater, and as a barrier for air and noise pollution. This function is useful for maintaining the city environment so that it remains beautiful and healthy.

➤ Socio-Cultural Function

The existence of Green Open Space causes people to have a place that can be used as a place to live, gather, communicate, and express themselves through the existing local culture.

➤ Economic Function.

Private Green Open Space can also be used to grow various fruit plants, flowers, and vegetables whose results can be used as a source of income such as in agriculture, plantations and tourism.

➤ Aesthetic Function

In addition to the functions mentioned above, the existence of green open space also has an equally important use, namely as a support for the beauty, vibrancy and comfort of the city.

B. Benefits of Green Open Space.

Based on its use and function, Green Open Space can be distinguished into having direct benefits, namely benefits that are perceived to be useful, such as a beautiful and comfortable recreational park, flower garden, or orchard, and indirect benefits, namely benefits that can be felt longer, such as clean air, a sustainable environment and more water availability. Other benefits are absorbing carbon dioxide (CO₂), so that it can suppress air pollution, maintain the condition of water in the surrounding environment, resist

algae, because the trees planted can reduce air temperature and humidity, also affect wind speed, and, as a habitat for wildlife, therefore can continue to support the local ecosystem, and act as a climate amelioration to provide coolness to urban areas that are hot due to reflection of solar radiation from buildings, asphalt and steel. Therefore, some of the benefits of Green Open space can be mentioned as follows. :

➤ *City Park*

It can be enjoyed by all people in the city environment as well as environmental guardians, groundwater storage and erosion and flood prevention.

➤ *Recreational Parks*

It functions similarly to a city park, but is more focused as a recreational place and is generally paid.

➤ *Nature Park*

That is an area that functions as a place for nature conservation and is also used for tourism and nature recreation.

➤ *Urban Forest*

According to Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 63, of 2002, concerning Urban Forests, Article 27 paragraph (1) Urban Forests are also used for recreation, sports, education, germplasm preservation, and cultivation of non-timber forest products

C. Humanist Open Space as a Healing Environment.

Humanist Open Space refers to the concept of green open space planning that is not only environmentally friendly and sustainable but also considers the comfort and safety of all living things of its users. This approach emphasizes the harmonious integration between, buildings, Urban Green Open Spaces and the surrounding environment, and focuses on coexistence between humans and animals who use these spaces. This approach emphasizes the importance of harmonious integration between buildings, urban landscapes and the environment with a focus on improving coexistence between humans and animals.

In urban planning, the concept of Green Open Space includes planning landscapes that simultaneously benefit humans and ecosystems, this includes planning parks, gardens and other green spaces that provide opportunities for humans to connect with nature, as well as support the health and welfare of local wildlife. Overall, Humanistic Green Space is an effort to create a balance between environmental sustainability, animal welfare, and human welfare in the planning and maintenance of Green Open Spaces.

Some of the characteristics of a Humanistic Green Open Space are as follows;

➤ *Accessibility*

A humane Green Open Space must be easily accessible to the public, including those with limited mobility or other accessibility needs.

➤ *Diversity*

It should consist of various types of environments including quiet environments for relationships, active spaces for sports and entertainment, and spaces for socializing.

➤ *Quality*

Green Open Space must be well maintained, and provide necessities such as toilets, seating areas and high-quality showers.

➤ *Security*

Green spaces should be safe and comfortable with adequate lighting, clear directional signs, and city-squares for emergencies.

➤ *Connectivity*

Public green spaces must be well connected to different parts of the city, with easy access for pedestrians, bicycles, or public transport.

➤ *Biodiversity*

Open spaces must protect the presence of plants and animals, which supports the health and ecological balance of the city.

➤ *Inclusivity*

Green Space must be inclusive and accepting for people from all walks of life, age groups and backgrounds. different socio-economic backgrounds.

➤ *Community Involvement*

Green spaces must provide opportunities for community involvement and socialization, foster a sense of belonging and have positive interactions among residents.

➤ *Sustainability*

Green spaces must be planned with sustainability aspects in mind, with the use of environmentally friendly materials, as well as measures to minimize environmental impacts or damage.

➤ *Ability to Adapt*

Green spaces must have the ability to adapt to the changing needs and preferences of society, and in the long term, maintain flexibility in the type of activities and their use.

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III. METHODOLOGY

This research uses a descriptive qualitative method, with literature studies and related references. Visual observations also made such as surveying the location of object , taking on site photos, which aims to find information that is as detailed as possible with the hope that the more the data obtained, the better the quality of the research produced.

A. Data Collection

The data collection for the purpose of this research, two types of data were collected as follows :

-Primary Data collection ;

Data collection through direct surveys of the user, by asking questions about preferences, perception and first hand experiences of the users.

-Secondary data collection.

Data collection through literatures, academic journals, previous research, policies ,rules and regulations published by the local government as well as related institutions.

B. Data Analysis.

Data analysis is the systemic process of inspecting, cleansing, transforming data to extract useful insight and support decision making.(1) . In this research descriptive data is analyze and interpreted to obtain a clear picture on the present condition in order to achieve a better solution for the on location problem.

C. Research location

This research is carried out in Situ Gintung Area, East Ciputat District, Pisangan Village, South Tangerang City, Banten Province. It is located just outskirts of Jakarta and can be reached by public or private transportation.

Fig 1 : Location of Situ Gintung Area.
Source : Google maps.accessed Dec.2024

Fig 2. Airal view of Situ gintung
Source : Google earth Pro. accessed Sept.2024.

IV. DISCUSSION AND RESULT

A. Present Condition of Situ Gintung

Fig 3: Main Entrance of Situ Gintung
Source : kompasiana.com-accessed Dec.2024

Fig 4 : Portal at the Main Entrance of Situ Gintung
Source : kompasiana.com

Fig 5 : Jogging Track Near the Main Entrance
Source : kompasiana .com. accessed Dec 2024.

Fig 6 : What is Left of Situ Gintung Island, Once was around 1.5 Hectare.
Source : Personal documentation – July 2024.

Fig 7 : The Dam that was Built after the Disaster.
Source : kompasiana.com- accessed Des 2024.

Fig 8 : Spillway of the New Dam,
Source : Personal documentation July 2024.

Fig 9 : Jogging Track Around Situ Gintung
Source : Personal documentation -july 2024

Fig 10 : A Fishing Site in Situ Gintung
Source : Personal Documentation – July 2024

Fig 11 : Monument to Commemorate the 2009 Disaster.
Source: Personal documentation – September 2024.

Fig 12 : Fishing, a Favorite Pastime in Situ Gintung
Source : Personal documentation – July 2024

B. Research Findings

Years after the disaster that happened in 2009, based on the photos review above, it can be seen that most of the a lot of improvement needed to be done to , the main entrance to make it more accessible, lack of outdoor elements , to make the jogging track , more enjoyable, so that Situ Gintung can better function as humanistic green space that can meet the the needs of its users in order to boost their health and well being , in addition to being a place of relaxation and recreation that is urgently needed by every individual who visits the Area.

C. Supporting Policies.

The Government has stipulated several law as well as regulation that can be used to support the improvement of Situ Gintung area such as:

- Law 23/1977 concerning basic provisions for environmental management.
- Law no.7/2024 regarding water resources management.
- Law no.26/2007 concerning spatial law
- Minister of Home affairs regulation No.1/2007 concerning the arrangement of of green open spaces in urban areas.

Despite of the stipulated law and regulation , violation of the Greenb Greenbelt area of 50 m from the edge of the reservoir still occurred. the Greenbelt in the form of jogging track is only around 1.5 to 2.00 meters.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Humanistic green open space are urban areas designed to foster social interaction mental well-being and environmental sustainability, as they serve as communal facilities for recreation , education and socialization, promoting harmony between humans and nature . Based on the research findings and supporting policies, the researcher

came into conclusion that, in order create a humanistic green open space it is important to improve the conditions of Situ Gintung, make it more humanistic and sustainable. Therefore in improving situ Gintung area, it is recommended to focus on the following strategies :

- Accessibility to the spaces have to be made easily reachable for all visitor, ensuring, safe pathways and transport option.
- Creating a multi-use areas, by creating a versatile spaces for activities such as sports , picnics and community events.
- Use Natural elements to integrate diverse vegetation to enhance aesthetic appeal and provide a calming environment.
- Involved the community to in the planning process to reflect their needs and preferences.
- Organized activities for the community community , such as concerts, weekend markets to draw people together and strengthen community bond.

Humanistic Green Open Spaces , have to be carefully managed, because they play a crucial role in mitigating urban stress, offering residents a refuge from city life and enhancing overall mental health.

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